

Article

Secondary Education and the Girl Child in Purulia District: A Case study of Enrollment of Kharia Girls

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Abstract

The paper intends to study the current enrolment status of Kharia girls in Purulia district.

Key terms Criminal Tribes, Enrolment, Girl Child

,Primary Education, Secondary Education, Kharia

Introduction

While Primary Education is a basic enabling factor for participation and freedom, for trading a life with dignity and overcoming basic deprivation, secondary education is the gateway for prosperity, for transforming the economy and establishing social justice in any country. It opens the world of work to the youth of the country and contributes to socio economic development of the Community.

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Secondary Education is a crucial stage in the educational hierarchy as it prepares the students for higher education and also the world of work. Classes IX and X constitute the secondary stage, whereas classes XI and XII are designated as the higher secondary stage. The normal age group of the children in secondary classes is 14-16 whereas it is 16-18 for higher secondary classes. The rigor of the secondary and higher secondary stage, enables Indian students to compete successfully for education and for jobs globally. Therefore, it is absolutely essential to strengthen this stage by providing greater access and also by improving quality in a significant way. With the liberalization and globalization of the Indian economy, the rapid changes witnessed in scientific and technological world and the general need to improve the quality of life and to reduce poverty, it is essential that schools leavers acquire a higher level of knowledge and skills than what they are provided in the eight years of elementary education, particularly when the average earning of a secondary school certificate holder is significantly higher than that of a person who has studied only up to class VIII.

The National Policy on Education (1986) and its Programme of Action (1992), inter alia states that access to secondary education will be widened with emphasis of enrolment of girls', scheduled castes and scheduled tribe particularly in science, commerce and in vocational streams.

Following the Constitutional mandate to universalize elementary education, and the success of Sarva Siksha Abhiyan, it has become essential to put this vision forward to move towards universalize of secondary education. The committee to universalize secondary education constituted by the Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) in 2005 suggested urgently taking up a program on secondary education. Accordingly the Government of India has launched a centrally sponsored scheme to universalize access to and improved quality of

education at secondary stage, called Rastriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan.¹

The Hon'ble Prime Minister, Dr. Manmohan Singh, in his Independence Day Speech, in 2007 has, inter-alia, stated that, special attention would need to be paid to Districts with SC/ST/OBC/Minority concentration. He also stated that, we are setting out a goal of universalizing secondary education. The vision for secondary education is to make good quality education available, accessible and affordable to all young persons in the age group of 14-18 years. With this vision in mind, the following is to be achieved

The scheme, Rastriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan, was launched in March, 2009 with the objective to enhance access to secondary education and to improve its quality. The implementation of the scheme started from 2009-10. It is envisaged to achieve an enrolment rate of 75% from 52.26% in 2005-06 at secondary stage within 5 years of implementation of the scheme by providing a secondary school within a reasonable distance of any habitation. The other objectives include improving quality of education imparted at secondary level through making all secondary schools conform to prescribed norms, removing gender, socio-economic and disability barriers, providing universal access to secondary level education by 2017, i.e., by the end of 12th Five Year Plan and achieving universal retention by 2020 and Provide access to secondary education with special references to economically weaker sections of the society, the educationally backward, the girls and the disabled children residing in rural areas and other marginalized categories like SC, ST, OBC and Educationally Backward Minorities (EBM)

Rastriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan (i) gave special focus on micro planning (ii) preference to Ashram schools for upgradation (iii) preference to areas with concentration of SC/ST/Minority for

opening of schools (iv) special enrolment drive for the weaker section (v) more female teachers in schools; and (vi) separate toilet blocks for girls.

In this backdrop, the objective of the present study is to examine the current enrolment status of secondary education of de-notified tribal girls in the district of Purulia. In this respect it can be mentioned here that Purulia is a district which have 20 community development blocks and 19 community development blocks were declared as educationally backward blocks (EBBs) out of these 20 blocks. Educationally Backward Blocks means a block where the level of rural female literacy is less than the national average (46.58%) and the gender gap in literacy is above the national average (21.7%) according to census 20012. And also those Blocks of districts that have at-least 5% SC/ ST population and SC/ ST female literacy rate below 10% shall also be taken up.

The concept of de notified criminal tribe

Before we proceed further, let us examine the concept of de notified criminal tribe. According to Verrier Elwin, the history of tribals dates back to where history of India starts.³ In real sense they are the communities dwelling nearby a mountain range and forests. During the British rule, a need emerged to utilize more of coal and wood, mainly for the railways and only for the building of British empire in India and in UK. This was the time when traditional land rights of the tribal were challenged. Their habitat, the forests, was regarded as a resource owned by the government. It was no longer the community ownership of tribals. The British policy, naturally, gave rise to stiff resistance from the tribals and as a result many fierce battles were fought against the British by tribals throughout the period. It was difficult even for the British rule to bring the tribals on record, gazette them and give them an identity. Before 1931 all the census reports by the

British used the term 'animists' (animal worshipers) for the tribals.⁴

Secondly, as railways and telegraphs were built / introduced in the 1850s such networks became redundant. The colonial authorities grew nervous about people who moved around, carrying intelligence they could not control directly. In the aftermath of the Sepoy Rebellion of 1857, these former allies were seen as potential enemies. In 1871, an Act was passed for "the notification of criminal tribes."⁵

Criminal Tribes Act of 1871 notified about 150 tribes along with the Kharia tribe, who traditionally collected food from the forest became criminals with the stroke of a pen around the country as "criminal".⁶ The upshot of this was that people at large tended to regard these tribes as criminal by birth. These "Criminal Tribes" were notified in a Gazette.

The main aim of the 1871 Act was to keep an eye on the activities of the criminal tribes. A constant surveillance over and vigilance about their activity was planned; but it was not the intention or object of this act to check the nomadism of these people, as that nomadism or moving from one place to another was not regarded in any way objectionable and harmful by the society.

The aim of the act was to control the crime and help the members of criminal tribes to reform and rehabilitate themselves. This act gave wide-ranging powers to the provincial government. The provincial governments were authorized to declare any group of people who were incorrigible criminals a Criminal Tribe. This act provided for maintenance of register in which the names and other particulars of all the adult members of a tribe were written. Further, they were required to register the information about births and deaths.

Some of them were required to report at regular intervals to the police station. From time to time a policeman used to take a round of their colonies and take roll-call of all the members. The 1871 Act had no specific plans for the reform of these people.

In 1902-3 a high powered Police Commission went into the matters in minute details. On the basis of the report submitted by the commission, the Government of India passed a new Act regarding Criminal Tribes in the year 1911. In accordance with this Act schedules were prepared for various criminal tribes and these schedules were complete in each respect.

In these, there were personal identification marks and the thumb impressions of each of the members of the Tribe.

This was done with a view to track down the criminals with ease. Besides the more notorious members of the tribe were put under very strict observation; their activities were minutely watched. Under this act provincial governments were given special instructions for the control of these tribes. The provincial governments were given powers to make suitable amendments in the Act in the light of their experiences.

From many aspects the 1911 act was defective and contained many loop holes. Basically in aim and intent it was preventive and not corrective. There were virtually no attempts in it to reform and rehabilitate the present criminals.

Therefore the 1911 Act was replaced by a new Act in 1924. The 1924 act empowered the provincial governments to declare criminal tribes and prepare a list of their members, having identification mark and thumb impression of each member. Besides, a check was put on the migratory instinct of the tribals. They were not to leave their place without prior permission of the police.

So, beginning from the year 1871 to the dawn of independence, a number of Acts regarding Criminal Tribes were passed and many amendments there to made to make them effective and help in checking the crime and control of the activities of the tribals.

After 1947, the national government paid serious attention to the problem and a number of committees were set up to go into the matter.

The basic theoretical and practical drawback in all previous thinking on the matter was the fact that these persons were deemed criminal by birth and it was believed that no matter what their opportunities or facilities they could not help being criminal. Therefore nothing could be done to bring them back to normal life and wean them away from criminality.

In this connection U.P. Government set up a high power Committee under the Chairmanship of Shri V.N. Tewari to go into the various aspects of the life of criminal tribes. After discussing the pros and cons of various proposals it came to the conclusion that the first and foremost imperative for any possible improvement in the condition of tribals is that the appellation 'criminal' should be dropped.

This unnecessarily stigmatized these people and prejudiced others to them. In the words of the Committee: "The removal of the appellation criminal will have salubrious psycho-social impact upon the children of these tribes.

This will help to eliminate from the minds of these people antisocial feelings and sentiments, because they will be relieved of the stigma and evil of considering themselves criminals and also relieved of the painful obligation of registering themselves with the police as soon as they attained the age of 15."

On the basis of this and many other reports of the committee and recommendations of social scientists and criminologists, the Bombay Criminal Tribes Act was repealed in 1949.

With the repeal of the Criminal Tribes Act 1924, on August 31, 1952, i.e. 'de-notified' the tribal communities, 22, 68,348 persons known as members of the criminal tribes in India were freed of the stigma of born criminality. Their status in society in terms of Article 15 of our Constitution, prohibiting discrimination on ground of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth, was recognized as co-equal with other communities. Ex-criminal tribes now enjoy all fundamental rights and their movements are not restricted to any settlement.

They are not subjected to any enhanced punishment for an offence simply because they belong to a certain tribe. The constitution lays down that the State shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and in particular of the scheduled castes and scheduled tribes and protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation. In terms of this directive the Government of India, State Governments and some Welfare Organisations are making every effort to settle the members of ex-criminal tribes as honest, peaceful and law-abiding citizens.⁷

The Kharias

In Purulia the Kharia tribe is known as de-notified criminal tribe. Kharia tribe in the district of Purulia is known as Hill Kharia. The Hill Kharias are confined to inhospitable hilly areas of Chhotonagpur, Mayurbhanj, Singhbhum and Manbhum.

Purulia was a part of Mnbhum upto 1956 and in 1956 it became a district in West Bengal. Hill Kharias of the Purulia district are the offshoot that migrated generations ago from Manbhum. All

Kharias of the Purulia district are found using the title Sabbar/Savar without any exception.⁸

Several important studies have been made on this tribe. One of the earliest comes from E T Dalton's 'Descriptive ethnology of Bengal' 1872. As per ET Dalton Hill Kharias in Purulia district are closely related with Santals, Hos, Asur, Kora, Malpaharia, and Munda, Oraon. All are (including Hill Kharias) belong to a single Munda stock, known variously as pre Dravidian or proto-Australoid. Hill Kharias are also included in that proto Australoid group. So it may be stated that the Hill Kharias is originally a branch of the great Mundari stock of proto-australoid race. Though all tribes such as Santals, Hos, Malpahari, Asur, Kora, Kharia have originated from same single stock but from the numerical point of view the Kharias are inferior to other tribes.⁹ The Munda group is still sometimes called the Kolarian group also. And they are apparently from Kolarian group.¹⁰ After that HH Risley published 'The Tribes and Caste of Bengal' in 1891. In 1916 V.R. Russel published his volume of 'The tribes and caste of Central Province of India.'

The most important and detailed study of the tribe came in two volumes of 'The Kharias' by SC Roy in 1937.¹¹ SC Roy recorded three distinctive divisions of Kharia tribe. Hill Kharia, Delki kharia and Dudh Kharia. These three section of the Kharia are at different levels of development and culture. The economy as well as social customs of the Hill Kharias are more primitive than their counterparts. These Hill Kharias called themselves as Savar or Sabbar. SC ROY also recorded that some old Hill Kharia called themselves as Savar as per the names of their first ancestor and ancestress Sabbar Burha and Sabbar Burhi¹².

Linguistically the language of the Hill Kharias belongs to Kolarian or Mundari branch of the austric family of language. Until the end of the nineteenth century the Kharias of Purulia district

spoke a language that was similar to the Mundari speech.

Some specimen words of that ancient language as collected by Sri Gagan Chandra Banerjee, Sub-Deputy Collector and published from Bengal secretariat press, Calcutta, in 1894 are given below.

Pe: Boiled rice

Koter: Bird

Bilung: Salt

The English sentence "I am a Kharia" would be translated into the ancient Kharia language as "Ing Kharia Heking". However they have adopted the Bengali dialect today as mother tongue and consequently the translation of the previous sentence has been "mui ekta Kharia".

It appears that within the last 150 years (approx) the Kharias living in the district of Purulia have forgotten their language and adopted Bengali as their mother tongue and in the process they have created a dialect of their own which is nothing but corrupt Bengali with a little mixture of words of their ancestral language and a pronunciation peculiar to themselves.¹³

In Purulia district Kharia tribe lives in 10 (ten) Community Development Blocks (CD blocks) out of 20 Community Development Blocks. Name of those blocks where the Kharia tribe people live are as follows.:

1. Arsha 2. Balarampur 3. Barabaza 4. Bandwan 5. Hura

6. Kashipur 7. Manbazar-1 8. Manbazar-2 9. Pancha 10. Purulia-I ; 11148 Sabars live in 177 villages of the above mentioned ten blocks in Purulia district.¹⁴

Out of these 10 Community Development blocks where Kharia tribe (de-notified tribe) live, two numbers of community development blocks is studied to know the current enrolment status of secondary education of Kharia tribe (de-notified tribe)

girls in the district of Purulia viz Bandwan and Manbazar II.

Bandwan community development block has highest percentage of tribal population in the district which is (51.07 percent) of total population of the block followed by Manbazar II which have (48.96 percent), of total population of the block.¹⁵ . Bandwan has 142 sector areas and it has 8 numbers of Gram Panchayats, 135 numbers of village and 135 numbers of Mouzas.

Out of those 135 numbers of villages Kharia tribes live in only 39 villages and approximate 2500 Kharia tribe people live in those villages.

Enrolment of tribal girls in secondary schools of Purulia district

In Bandwan block, we have the following 11 secondary and higher secondary school where girls children from various villages of Bandwan Blocks can be studied at secondary level.

Bandwan Girl's High School (H.S.)

Dr. A.N. Jha High School, Bandwan

Hetyakole High School, Bandwan

Pargela High School, Bandwan

Talpat Adarsha High School, Bandwan

Ghagra K.S. High School Bandwan

Kuilapal S.S. High School, Bandwan

Kunchia High School, Bandwan

Dhadka Anchalik High School, Bandwan

Chirudih V.N. High School, Bandwan

Rajgram High School, Bandwan

Gangamanna High School, Bandwan

No girl children of Kharia tribe have enrolled in anyone of the above mentioned school.

MANBAZAR-II community development block has 116 sector areas, 7 numbers of Gram Panchayat, 136 numbers of villages and 315 numbers of Mouzas.

Out of those 136 villages Kharia lives in 31 villages and here also approximate 2500 Kharia tribe people are found.

Manbazar II block has the following 16 numbers of secondary and higher secondary school where girls children from various villages of Manbazar II Blocks can be studied at secondary level.

Aguibil High School, Manbazar II

Ankro High School (H.S.), Manbazar II

Bargoria High School, Manbazar II

Bari High School, Manbazar II

Basantapur Adinasi High School, Manbazar II

Belgeria High School, Manbazar II

Boro High School (H.S.), Manbazar II

Chandanpur High School, Manbazar II

Dharampur Girls High School, Manbazar II

Dighi High School, Manbazar II

Golapara R.N. High School (H.S.), Manbazar II

Jamtoria High School (H.S.), Manbazar II

Jorobari High School, Manbazar II

Khariduar High School, Manbazar II

Kumari High School, Manbazar II

In Manbazar II block, I could only find two girl children of the Kharia community who are enrolled in school.

1)Mangal Sabar's daughter, Rahamoni Sabar, lives in Kheriadih village.she read in Class IX in Chandanpur High School.16

2) Rekha Sabar, Father's name Kartik Sabar, lives in Vill- Hatiramgora, P.O.- Mamro read in class IX in Ankro High School (H.S.)

From the above data, we find that very few of the Kharia tribal girls have been enrolled in school.

In 1997, Chandidas Mukhopadhyay wrote, Hill Kharia of Purulia are possibly the most backward of all tribal communities settled in West Bengal. They are also categorized as born criminals by the outgroup communities of the locality. Categorized this way the Hill Kharia bears a stigma- the stigma of criminality.17 As per Goffman's definition, stigma as an attribute that is deeply discrediting- that reduce the processor in our mind from whole and usual person to a tainted discounted one.18 The stigma effect the life of the Hill Kharias in Purulia and they are not treated as normal and are subjected to unfair persecutions and discrimination by the outgroup people. Regarding education Mukhopadhyay wrote the Kharias are a largely illiterate community. Female literacy is almost nil among Kharias. Those Kharias who have some education live in the villages of Manbazar and most

of the illiterates are from the hilly region of Bandwan.19

In spite of that, it is disappointing despite programs like Sarva Siksha Abhiyan, National Program of Education for Girls' at Elementary Level (NPEGEL) with special focus on Scheduled tribe girls, Right to Education Act 2009 and Rastriya Madhyamik Siksha Abhiyan, the enrollment of tribal girls in secondary education is poor. The Ministry of Backward Classes Welfare Department WB also introduced many scholarship schemes to tribal children to make secondary education accessible to all tribal children. Schemes are, pre matric level book grant scheme to Sc/St students exclusively funded by the state government, hostel grant for ST children residing in school attached hostels. Merit scholarship scheme for students reading in class IX and X with assistance of central government. Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Government of India, sanctions grant-in-aid to different NGOs working for welfare of the Scheduled Tribes. In spite of all these the current enrolment status of Kharia girls' (de notified tribe) at secondary education is really a disappointing factor.

Concluding Remarks

To bring the light of education to more tribal girls, we need to urgently think about ways and means to make education more attractive to the parents of Kharia girls and the girls themselves.1)In this age of globalization, civil society organizations, like NGO s can come forward with innovative programmes which will make education attractive for children. Secondly government announce programs for scheduled tribe as a whole without segregating the different scheduled tribe and without making field work regarding the necessary requirement of different tribal community because different tribal community have different development level. So, Union Government and state government should prepare plan and program

separately for the notified tribe in Purulia district in this regard. Thirdly regular monitoring of implementation of plan is required. Fourthly, education should be intimately linked to generation of earnings. From the very beginning, secondary education should be dovetailed with vocational education. The emphasis should be on 'earn and learn'.

Notes

¹ Accessed from website <http://www.mhrd.gov.in> on 27/09/2013

² Accessed from web page, <http://www.ssa.nic.in>. as accessed on 4th April 2012

³ Accessed from website www.vandematam.com on 14.01.2013

⁴ Ibid

⁵ Bhattacharya Jagabandhu, July-Dec 1996, an article "Swadhinata Sangrame Sabar" from 'Bortika' edited by Mahasweta Devi Sameeksha press, Kol-12 p3-4

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⁷ Dey, Suresh Short essay on Acts Concerning Criminal Tribes in India, published in website www.tribes.in

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⁸ Mukherjee T N, 1981, an article "The offshoot that migrated Generations ago: A Study on the Hill Kharias of West Bengal" from The Profile of the Marginal and Pre-

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⁹ Roy, S. C., 1937, *The Kharias*, op. cit., p. 3

¹⁰ Dalton, E.T., 1891, *The Kharias, Descriptive ethnology of Bengal*, Office of the superintendent of Government Printing Calcutta, p.p. 466-472

¹¹ Upadhyay, V. S. The Hill Kharia of Singbhum: a problematic study. P181

¹² Gupta, SP the Primitive Hill Kharia- struggling for existence. P 212

¹³ Mitra, S. P., WBCS (Executive) a Govt (W.B.) report on Kharia sabar of Purulia District 1999

¹⁴ Data provided by the Kharia savaar Kalyan Samity an NGO at Rajnagarh in Purulia WB

¹⁵ Accessed from website <http://www.ecoinsee.org/> on 28.09.2013

¹⁶ Accessed from website <http://www.anagrasarkalyan.gov.in> on 28.09.2013

¹⁷ Mukhopadhyay, Chandidas 1997, *Kharias-The Victims of Social Stigma*, KP Bagchi & Company, Kolkata, p. 1

¹⁸ Goffman, Erving, 1963, *Stigma Note on the Spoiling Identity*, Eagle wood cliff, New Jersey, p-3

¹⁹ Mukhopadhyay, Chandidas 1997, *Kharias-The Victims of Social Stigma*, KP Bagchi & Company, Kolkata, p. 1